

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D3.8 Public Database for Researchers

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Project Information	
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Deliverable Information	
DELIVERABLE N° AND TITLE	D3.8 Public Database for Researchers
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE¹	OTHER
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BENEFICIARY NUMBER AND NAME	3 - NLR
AUTHORS	Roalt AALMOES
CONTRIBUTORS	-
WORK PACKAGE N°	3
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¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web
CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
CI=Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

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1. Executive Summary

This document describes the collection of research data that has been obtained in the ANIMA project. Purpose of this collection is to save these datasets for future research and future researchers, as *Open Access* data. Only datasets are provided that are created or gathered by ANIMA partners, or been given to ANIMA and can be made available so they may be used without additional costs by other parties. In some instances, the datasets are made available after a limited time after the project, to allow ANIMA researchers to make (unique) publications based upon this research data.

2. Introduction

Publishing raw research data as *Open data* or *open access* is generally considered a good academic practice to validate existing research results, and encourages new research based on reuse of existing data, or verify other data sources. In the European ANIMA project, the ANIMA partners have done extensive research, and gathered data in various ways and from different sources. This data has resulted in a number of publications as ANIMA deliverables, journal and conference articles, and other publications as well. The data itself is considered to be an additional result of the ANIMA project, and for this reason, it should be made available as well to those who have interest in it. In the ANIMA Data management Plan, an extensive analysis is made of the data that is created in the ANIMA project [1]. This document will describe those datasets that are considered useful for future research or researchers, and can be made publicly available. This document describes those datasets that is now, or will be made available to the public in the near future.

Not all data can be made available. Some of the data is gathered from other parties, such as airports, civil aviation authorities, or government agencies, with a dedicated use for a specific (ANIMA) study. Or data is retrieved from commercial agencies with limited or no rights to (re)publish. Another limitation is related to European privacy rights as they are written down in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)³. Among others elements, this regulation prevents the identification of individuals from published datasets without their consent. Any identifiable data (or a combination of data that may identify a person) should therefore be removed or reduced in detail. For example, an exact GPS location of a mobile application may refer to a single individual, but providing a postal code instead may prevent this identification. Finally, some datasets may be considered to be of limited use for be included in the

³ See also: <https://gdpr.eu/>

database. The reasons for not including this data may be the limited size of the dataset, a very specific research that is may not be practical to use later on, or any other practical limitation. It is up to the researchers of the ANIMA studies to make this decision whether to provide a dataset for future open data usage.

Not all datasets provided in this document will be made available immediately. In some instances, the datasets are made available after a limited time after the project, to allow ANIMA researchers to make (unique) publications based upon this research data. This requirement is necessary to comply with publishers' regulations. In some other instances, the (ANIMA) study or data is not yet completed, or is still in the process of being published at the time of publication of this deliverable.

3. Description of research data

The following table describes the datasets that have been gathered in the ANIMA project and made available as *open data*. The table contains the following columns:

- A *subtask* that identifies the original ANIMA subtask in which the data was obtained. Mainly useful for ANIMA partners.
- A short *description* of the research data.
- A reference to the corresponding ANIMA deliverable. This deliverable will provide the context of the study and what type of data can be expected in the given dataset.
- A *state* indicating whether the data is already available or when it is expected to become available.
- A primary *point-of-contact* for the data.
- A *link* to the data in case the data is made available. Note that the data will be made available on the Zenodo⁴ Open Science platform. If this column states "Upon Request", the dataset will not be published on Zenodo but is available upon request via the provided point of contact.

Please note that those datasets that are not yet available on Zenodo, will be published on this platform at the time of their release.

⁴ See <https://www.zenodo.org/>

Subtask	Description	Deliverable	State	Point-of-contact	Location
ST3.1.2	Evaluations of previous interventions in improving quality of life	D3.6	Published	kuhlmann@zeusgmbh.de (ZEUS)	https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4655400
ST3.2.1	Fairness questionnaire survey	D3.9	Available after journal article publication	Dominik.Hauptvogel@dlr.de (DLR)	
ST3.2.3	Studies on Virtual and Auralisation tools: Laboratory data from participants	D3.10	Available after journal article publication	catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr (CYU)	
ST4.2.1	Syntheses of aircraft noise obtained by computational methods	D4.5	Published	Ingrid.legriffon@onera.fr	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5524200
ST2.5	Case Study Ljubljana (Community Engagement)	D2.11	Published	info@nijz.si (NIJZ)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5604884
ST2.5	Case Study Cluj International Airport (Interdependencies): data used for performing the analyses within the case study will be provided, containing flight data	D2.11	Available Nov-2021	narcisa.burtea@comoti.ro (COMOTI)	
ST2.5	Case Study Cluj International Airport (Quality of Life): data with responses of residents will be provided.	D2.11	Available Nov-2021	narcisa.burtea@comoti.ro (COMOTI)	
ST2.5	Case Study Rotterdam Airport	D2.11	Published	roalt.aalmoes@nlr.nl (NLR)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5604661
ST2.5	Additional Case Study Quality of Life around Schiphol Airport during COVID-19	-	Available after journal article publication	roalt.aalmoes@nlr.nl (NLR)	
ST3.3.2	AnimApp Mobile application survey data	D3.4	Available Dec-2021	marki@vik.bme.hu (BME)	Upon request

4. Other data sources

The measurements and calculations in Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine, for land-use planning purposes done in the ANIMA were not based on open data, but on data from the Ukrainian CAA. Therefore, it cannot be shared. But some of this data is already available at NOMOS monitoring project on Ukrainian CAA website via <https://nomos.avia.gov.ua>

5. References

1. Data Management Plan Version 1, Laurent Leylekian, ANIMA Deliverable D5.4, 05/04/2018.